

POLITICAL SCIENCES

THE UNDERTAKING OF INTERNATIONAL RESPONSIBILITY DURING ARMED CONFLICTS

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ABSTRACT

Limiting the effects of military or civil conflicts has been a permanent concern of society, given that for a long-time wars were considered a legitimate instrument of the states for the settlement of their own interests.

The undertaking of international responsibility is a priority for the maintenance of peace and security worldwide, given that each state must preserve its sovereignty, but without acting in an absolute freedom that would limit that of other global actors. Ensuring compliance with international humanitarian norms can also be achieved through the application of coercive measures by states, individually or collectively.

Keywords: international responsibility, International Criminal Court, UN Security Council, conflict, crime of aggression, sanctions.

Introduction

Concern for the creation of a complex system to ensure compliance with humanitarian law has developed since 1949, with the adoption of the four Geneva Conventions, which acquired a universal character through their acceptance and implementation by both states and international organizations.

In international humanitarian law, the responsibility of both states and natural persons, in their capacity as their representatives, is engaged when they commit illegal acts that harm other states or their citizens and that constitute threats or violations to international peace and human rights (Popescu 2011, p. 152).

In this context, it can be considered that the responsibility of the states intervenes for the acts of all its public authorities, regardless of whether they are central or local and without distinguishing among legislative, executive or judicial functions.

The responsibility of states, but also of their representatives, is triggered either by the violation of the norms and principles of international humanitarian law, by non-compliance with treaties, conventions or customs, or as a result of the outbreak of armed conflict.

The Parliament can engage the responsibility of the state through the lack of transposition into the internal normative acts of the international regulations in the field of humanitarian law or through the omission to abrogate or modify the internal laws that contravene to the ratified conventions, while the judicial authorities can attract this responsibility if they pronounce sentences incompatible with international humanitarian law.

At the same time, the heads of state, government, ministers or other official persons can be held responsible in their capacity as representatives of the state, through the actions ordered or authorized by them or through their omissions, which is why the blame for the violations brought to the norms of international humanitarian law by the members of the state's armed forces is on them, if those forces are part of the state's structures.

1. States' responsibility

The international responsibility of states was enshrined for the first time in the Fourth Hague Convention on the Laws and Customs of War on Land of 1907 at art. 3, which stipulates that "*the belligerent party that would violate the provisions of the Regulation annexed to the Convention will be obliged to pay compensation, if necessary, and will be responsible for all the acts committed by the persons who are part of its armed forces*". This norm regarding the international responsibility of belligerent states was later taken over in article 91 of Additional Protocol I of 1977.

Also, provisions relating to the responsibility of states can be found in art. 146 of the Geneva Convention regarding the protection of civilians in time of war, according to which: "*States undertake to take any necessary legislative measures to establish criminal sanctions to be applied to persons who have committed or ordering to be committed serious crimes*".

In the Geneva Conventions, the responsibility for the violation of the rules of international humanitarian law was committed mainly to individuals and less to states, since the procedure by which states could be punished by an international court was not regulated.

However, even after the establishment of the international courts, their competence has a complementary character, considering that the internal jurisdiction of the states is arbitrary, in the sense that they have the main powers to establish and apply sanctions in the case of crimes that violate the rules of international humanitarian law.

On the international level, there is no overall regulation regarding the responsibility of states, a criminal code or a court that imposes on people from different countries the punishments established by international courts, the states being the ones that have the obligation to ensure the application of domestic law, through laws and mechanisms their jurisdictions.

In order for the legal responsibility of the states to be engaged, certain conditions must be met: there must be an illegal act manifested by an action or omission imputable to the state, through that act the principles or norms of IHL have been violated, there must be guilt, there must have been material or moral damage and

there must be a causal link between the illegal act and the result produced (Anghel și Anghel 2003, p. 131).

Thus, states are politically, materially or morally responsible for the actions of their authorities and officials and, as a result of damages caused by activities that are not prohibited by international law, the state's obligation to compensate results from the fact that the source of the damage is located on its territory under its control (Anghel și Anghel 2003, p. 133).

Among the sanctions of political nature enshrined in the UN Charter, the following can be mentioned: severance of diplomatic relations, exclusion or suspension of rights within international organizations, interruption of economic relations and communications, use of air, naval or land armed forces for demonstrative purposes or carrying out military operations based on the decision of the Security Council (United Nations Charter 1945, Art. 5-6, Art. 41-42).

Also, moral responsibility can be materialized by applying some sanctions to the people who committed the acts, which can be of a pecuniary nature. For example, Germany agreed to pay reparations to the victims of the Nazi camps, both for the material and moral damages caused.

On the other hand, the state can be materially liable both for its direct actions in violation of international law and for the damages caused by one of its nationals. In this case, the reparation of the material damage can be performed under two aspects: by paying compensation or by restoring the state to the situation prior to the commission of the illegal action, which can be manifested by the return of goods or values taken by the aggressor state in time of war from the territory of another state, victim of aggression.

2. The role of the International Criminal Court in the settlement of current disputes

The idea of establishing an international criminal court was realized by the resolution of the UN General Assembly no. 260 (III) of 1949, by which it requested the International Law Commission to rule on the possibility of establishing an international judicial body to try crimes provided for by international conventions, including the crime of genocide (A/RES/3/260 B 1948).

However, the adoption of the draft Statute drafted in 1953 by the committee appointed by the General Assembly based on UN Resolution no. 687 (VII) and which contained provisions relating to the creation of a Court based on a convention that would have an independent character, was postponed due to procedural considerations, which aimed at drafting a Code of crimes against the peace and security of mankind, as well as defining the notion the crime of aggression (A/RES/687(VII) (1952) 1952).

The establishment of this judicial body created certain advantages taking into account its international legal personality, but also the trial and sentencing of people who are guilty of violating humanitarian law by committing genocide, crimes against humanity, war and aggression.

In this sense, it is competent to exercise its powers on the territory of any state that is a party to the Statute and regardless of the nationality of the persons who

committed the crimes, without being considered to violate national sovereignty, since national judicial systems retain their prior right to investigate and judge international crimes, the role of the Court being only to complement the national jurisdiction (Dragoman și Ungureanu 2008, p. 761).

All the requests from the Court regarding cooperation, including those concerning arrests, collection of evidence or extradition, are dealt with first by national judicial systems and only to the extent that they prove ineffective, according to art. 17 of the Statute (Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998, Art. 17), will they be submitted to the attention of the Court. At the same time, the cooperation of the states with the Court for conducting investigations is a general obligation, which emerges both from the content of art. 86 (Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998), as well as from the other provisions of the Statute.

Through the lens of this cooperation, the possibility of judging international crimes by an independent institution was pursued, so that the punishment of the people guilty of committing them does not depend entirely on the national courts, which could be influenced by the political interests of the governments responsible for ordering the violation of international norms.

In this case, the Statute gives the Court authority to address requests to the states parties for cooperation, requests that will be sent through diplomatic channels or by any other method that they will designate on the occasion of ratification, accession, approval or acceptance, with the taking of the necessary measures to ensure the physical or mental state of victims, witnesses and their families, including measures to protect information (Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998, Art. 87, par. 1-4).

On the other hand, a major disadvantage arises in the situation where a state is not a party to the Statute, since it will have the obligation to cooperate with the Court only if it has previously signed an ad hoc arrangement or agreement to this effect (Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998, Art. 87, line (5) a)). However, if such an agreement has not been concluded, the Court will not have any jurisdiction over the persons of these states, as they are not obliged to comply with the obligations of cooperation.

The only way in which the persons guilty of committing the crimes provided for in the statute can be held accountable would be through referral by the Assembly of States Parties or by a state to the UN Security Council, which can intervene by applying the coercive measures provided for in Chapter VII from the UN Charter.

Among the states that refused to ratify the Statute there are the USA, Russia and China, respectively three of the permanent members of the Security Council. The lack of ratification by these states represents a gap in the achievement of the purpose for which the Court was established, since international crimes committed by their nationals will only be able to be tried on the basis of a previous bilateral agreement between them and the Court, i.e. only after expressing their consent to hand over the persons guilty of committing those acts.

In addition, the fair functioning of the Security Council cannot produce the desired effects, since the states parties to the Statute could request it to adopt coercive measures and hold accountable the citizens of permanent members who have committed international crimes, in which case the measures will not be implemented due to their blocking by exercising the right of veto.

The signing of the Statute by Russia and the USA only gives them the right to participate as observers in the Assembly of States Parties, according to art. 112, but the jurisdiction of the Court cannot be extended with regard to the sanctioning of the citizens of these states. Their judgment by the Court could be achieved if the state in whose territory the acts were committed or the state that is not a party to the Statute, but which accepted the court's jurisdiction, would express its consent, as provided for in article 12 of the Statute.

However, for the efficient functioning of the Court, it is necessary to express the intention of the states to cooperate for the transposition of the provisions of the Statute at the national level, but to the extent that their political interests will prevail, the competence of the Court will still remain limited.

A provision of the Statute that may create certain disadvantages in the sanctioning of persons guilty of committing international crimes, is that concerning the right of the Security Council to request the postponing of an investigation for a period of 12 months, through a resolution adopted in accordance with Chapter VII of UN Charter and addressed to the Court, an application which is renewable. (Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998, Art. 16).

If we refer to the composition of the Council and the partially undemocratic voting system, as well as the discriminatory way in which it has acted over time according to the political interests of the permanent members, it can be seen that this provision can affect the fulfilment of the Court's duties.

The abusive exercise of the right of veto through the extensive interpretation of certain situations that may fall under Chapter VII of the Charter, including those related to the violation of human rights, call into question the relations between the Security Council and the Court in terms of the correctness of the engagement of criminal liability of persons who commit international crimes.

The right conferred on the Council pursuant to art. 16 may determine the possibility for one of the permanent members who is not a party to the Statute and who does not wish to become one, to influence the jurisdiction of the Court in certain cases. In order to have a clear interpretation of the provisions of article 16, a detailed exposition of the cases in which the Council can request the postponement of an investigation, respectively the conditions under which it can make such a decision, is necessary.

3. Sanctioning the crime of aggression in order to ensure international security

A disadvantage in terms of the way of drafting the provisions of the Statute was determined for a long time by the lack of a clear definition of the "crime of aggression".

The notion of an act of aggression was defined for the first time in UN General Assembly Resolution no. 3314 from 1974 as "the use of force by a state against the sovereignty, territorial integrity or political independence of another state or in any manner that contravenes the Charter of the United Nations" (A/RES/3314(XXIX) 1974, Art. 1).

The content of article 3 of the resolution also defined the manifestations of the act of aggression, while in article 5 par. (2) it is stated that "the war of aggression is a crime against international peace. Aggression gives rise to international responsibility", provisions that were later included in article 8 bis of the Statute of the Court.

From the contents of the initial provisions, it appears that the responsibility for carrying out a war of aggression rests with the state, since the phrase "international responsibility" was provided, which cannot be interpreted as being the responsibility of a natural person. Thus, at the time when aggression was defined in an official UN document, the notion referred to an act committed by a state.

After the adoption of the Treaty of Rome in 1998, the crime of aggression was regulated in such a way that natural persons could also be prosecuted, but there were many disagreements both regarding its inclusion in the Statute and regarding the definition and the ways in which will initiate criminal prosecution in her case.

Initially, the permanent members of the UN Security Council did not agree on the procedures by which the Prosecutor of the Court could carry out investigations on his own initiative for the commission of the crime of aggression, independently of a resolution of the Council. In this case, it could be interpreted that their own political interests will be affected, given that they have been repeatedly accused of committing acts of aggression against other states such as: Russia's invasion of Georgia in 2008, the US invasion of Iraq of 2003 or the US airstrikes in Iraq in 1993, the US attack on Afghanistan in 2001, the NATO bombing of Serbia in 1998 (Scharf 2012, 358-362).

The adoption of such procedures within the Statute of the Court would have constituted a limitation of the right of veto that can block any resolution of the Council, which would contradict the own interests of the political or military leaders of these states.

Thus, following the Kampala Conference in 2010, following the revision of the Statute, the definition of the crime of aggression and the act of aggression was introduced. According to art. 8 bis, "the crime of aggression means the planning, initiation or execution by a person in a position of effective control or direction of the political or military actions of a state of an aggression which by its character, gravity and size constitutes a manifest violation of the United Nations Charter" (Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998, Art. 8 bis).

At the same time, during the Kampala Conference, discussions were held regarding the establishment of the body competent to qualify the action of a state as an act of aggression. The Security Council was nominated among the proposals, but if the amendment had been adopted in this form, it could have blocked any decision

that could have affected his political interests by defining certain acts as acts of aggression (Lascu 2016, p. 121).

As a method of compromise, it was established according to art. 15 bis and 15 ter for the prosecutor of the International Criminal Court to carry out the investigations regarding the crimes of aggression, but before starting them he is obliged to address the Security Council of the U.N. to pronounce on the existence or not of such an act and only if this body pronounces in the sense of qualifying the act of aggression as such, then the prosecutor will be able to start the investigative acts (Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998, Art. 15 bis, par. 6).

In addition, as I stated previously, the activity of the prosecutor can be suspended for one year, without carrying out any investigation in the case, if the Security Council requests this by resolution, according to article 16 of the Statute.

Although there is apparently no decision-making monopoly on the part of the Security Council, in practice, the conduct of investigations on one's own initiative by the prosecutor remains to be applied only at a conceptual level. Any of the permanent members of the UN Security Council would be interested in blocking the investigation of a crime of aggression in respect of which there is a notification of the Court's prosecutor, having the possibility to use their right of veto and prevent the start of investigations.

On the other hand, not only states with permanent membership in the UN Security Council can avoid the jurisdiction of the Court regarding the crime of aggression. According to the provisions contained in article 15 bis paragraph 4 of the Statute, the states that submit to the Registry of the Court a declaration of renouncing the recognition of the jurisdiction of this court can, in turn, avoid it, too (Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998, Art. 15 bis par. 4).

The same applies to states that are not parties to the Statute. According to the provisions of article 15 bis paragraph 5, the Court's jurisdiction is not applicable to them either in relation to their citizens or in relation to acts committed on their territory (Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998, Art. 15 bis par. 5).

The invasion of Ukraine by Russia in 2022 has once again led to the reorientation of states' attention to the crime of aggression. However, although the crime is provided for in the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, the court does not have jurisdiction to submit it to trial in the current situation.

Starting from the definition of the crime of aggression, the crime covers only a limited number of perpetrators, namely political or military leaders "in a position to effectively exercise control or direct the political or military action of a state" (Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court 1998, art. 8 bis., par. 1).

Also, the definition refers only to violations of the norms of the UN Charter, targeting the most serious crimes that concern the international community, without expressly mentioning which actions can be included in the category of the crime of aggression, as they were listed in the case of the act of aggression.

On the other hand, although the states that are parties to the Rome Statute can refer the Court to try the crime of aggression, Russia and Ukraine have not ratified the statute, which is why the jurisdiction of the Court cannot apply to them, as Russia cannot be forced to hand over to the persons who are guilty of committing that crime are tried, even if Ukraine would recognize the jurisdiction of the court under article 12 par. 3 of the Statute.

The Security Council has the right to find that the actions taken against Ukraine are the subject of the crime of aggression and could apply coercive measures, but given that Russia is one of the permanent members, it will block with the right of veto any sanction that could be applied to the people guilty of triggering the conflict.

In the case of Ukraine, various proposals for prosecuting the crime of aggression have been suggested. One of them aims to establish a tribunal similar to the one in Nuremberg that would pool the jurisdictions of several countries (Statement Calling For the Creation of a Special Tribunal for the Punishment of the Crime of Aggression Against Ukraine 2022, p. 2).

Also, another solution would be to establish a hybrid court, created on the basis of the agreement concluded between Ukraine and the United Nations, at the request of Ukraine and recommended by the General Assembly. It is thus considered that the General Assembly is the only one in a position to order measures when the activity of the Security Council is blocked by the abusive exercise of the right of veto (Trahan 2002).

Thus, in order to be able to extend the jurisdiction of the Court over the trial of the crime of aggression, it is necessary that all the states party to the Rome Statute ratify the amendments introduced regarding this crime, including those that are not parties to the statute, amendments that entered into force on July 17, 2018, with the adoption of resolution no. ICC-ASP/16/20/Res.5 (ICC-ASP/16/20/Res.5 2017).

Conclusions

In order to strengthen the independent and impartial status of the International Criminal Court, in the current unstable political context determined by the conflict between Russia and Ukraine, we consider it opportune to amend the provisions of the UN Charter in the parts related to the exercise of the right of veto by the permanent members or the total abrogation of the Charter and its replacement with a new normative act with the same legal force, which provides for the adoption of all decisions with a qualified majority within the UN General Assembly or the division of powers between the Security Council and the General Assembly regarding the imposition of measures to settle international disputes, without a distinction is also made between permanent and non-permanent members, so that any state can equally express its vote on international security issues and the sanctioning of parties involved in the triggering of armed conflicts.

In addition, it is necessary to change the regulations of art 15 bis of the Statute of the International Criminal Court regarding the powers of the Court's prosecutor, so that he can investigate the actions of the representatives of a state that falls under the scope of

the crime of aggression, without first notifying the Security Council in order to qualify from a legal point of view, committing an act as an act of aggression.

It is also a priority to repeal art. 16 of the Statute, so that the Council no longer benefits from the right to request by resolution the suspension of an investigation for one year, with the aim of avoiding in the future the permanent members from being held accountable for committing crimes of aggression.

On the other hand, another amendment must provide for the prohibition of the states parties to submit declarations of renunciation of the recognition of the jurisdiction of this court, being necessary at the same time to continue cooperation efforts at the international level to oblige all states to ratify the Rome Statute, including by applying political or economic sanctions to parties that refuse to ratify.

Considering all these legislative deficiencies on the basis of which the states avail themselves of the avoidance of the Court's jurisdiction, it can be considered that it is difficult to determine in which situations the amendments brought to the Treaty of Rome regarding the crime of aggression can be applied. The need to adopt a new normative framework for the reconfiguration of international institutions and organizations is imposed against the background of the resolution of ongoing conflicts, the sanctioning of the persons and states guilty of triggering them, but also with a view to limiting and preventing future new conflagrations that destabilize international law order.

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